



Additional file 13 (.pdf)

Figure S12: Distribution of markers, associations and QTLs according to MAF for 50K, 600K GBS, and ALL technologies. A) Number of markers, B) Proportion of markers, C) Proportion of Association, D) Proportion of QTLs